

UNRAVELING THE CONNECTION BETWEEN BUDGETING PRACTICES AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF START-UP BUSINESSES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 33

Issue 7

Pages: 776-784

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3202

DOI: 10.70838/pemj.330706

Manuscript Accepted: 02-22-2025

Unraveling the Connection Between Budgeting Practices and Financial Performance of Start-Up Businesses

Sarah Jane B. Orillosa,* Charlene Mae P. Acut, Hannah Shayne U. Cabante, Janna O. Trinidad

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Despite the critical role of budgeting in financial planning and control, many businesses, particularly start-up, struggle to establish effective budgeting practices, leading to inconsistent financial performance. This study examined the relationship between budgeting practices and financial performance in start-up businesses. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, with data collected from 75 start-up owners and managers using stratified random sampling technique. The study assessed the level of budgeting practices, the level of financial performance and the relationship between the variables. Findings indicate that start-ups demonstrate a very high level of budgeting practices, which corresponds with a high financial performance. Statistical analysis confirms a significant and positive relationship between budgeting practices and financial performance. These findings emphasized the need for entrepreneurs to adopt systematic budgeting practices - resource allocation, budget planning, financial forecasting, and budget control - to enhance financial performance as to profitability, growth in sales and liquidity.

Keywords: *budgeting practices, financial performance, start-up businesses*

Introduction

Inadequate budgeting practices exposes businesses to financial risks, thus weakening its financial performance. With this, Wang et al. (2023) highlighted that financial performance is often influenced by external factors such as economic conditions, regulatory changes, and market competition. Due to the perceived high risk associated with SMEs, financial institutions often hesitate to provide loans, forcing these businesses to rely on internal sources of funding or short-term credit (Beck et al., 2018). This limited access to finance constrains the growth potential of SMEs, preventing them from investing in innovation, expanding operations, or strengthening their market position (Ayyagari et al., 2020). Additionally, Ozturk and Aktas (2019) noted that firms exposed to economic downturns often experience drastic fluctuations in financial performance. These fluctuations, if not properly analyzed, may be misinterpreted as signs of operational inefficiency rather than the result of external economic pressures.

Countless African firms have failed due to poor financial performance. Uganda has a high failure rate, with over 30% of SMEs failing to reach their third anniversary (Afunadula, 2018). These failure rates indicate poor financial performance, which cannot be overlooked. In addition, Agbana et al. (2023) discovered that credit and liquidity risks have a substantial impact on the performance of Nigeria's listed deposit money banks, owing to weak risk management and failure to meet prudential liquidity, solvency, and capital ratio requirements. This affirms Edem (2017) which concluded that illiquidity and excess liquidity constitute financial problems that can quickly wear down a bank's return base because they both impair bank performance.

The success of businesses depends on their ability to budget, particularly when tracking and assessing performance (Mutabari & Warui, 2023). However, one specific budgeting practice that frequently comes up as a source of concern for small business owners is the neglect to include irregular or unforeseen spending (Grzesiak, 2023). Such budgeting practice problem has a vital impact on financial performance (Otoo, 2024). Moreover, Ariza et al. (2023) claimed that businesses' financial performance problems are a result of adopting ineffective budgeting practices.

A 2021 study by Dela Cruz and Gonzales examined financial factors influencing the performance of Philippine Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) which highlighted that limited access to financing and capital significantly hampers the growth and profitability of these enterprises. The study emphasized the need for improved financial support mechanisms to enhance MSME performance. Moreover, a study conducted by Dolorso (2023) in the Philippines concluded that newly established businesses do not have a well-developed budget/financial plan that can aid them which may lead to a possible loss and it can directly affect the business. Additionally, a study conducted in Cebu stated that MSMEs did not observe the proper means of budgeting the resources and assets of the business have a progressively critical impact on the company's financial presentation (Anoos et al., 2020).

This study addresses the limited research on budgeting practices among start-up business in Region XII, Philippines, and their impact on financial performance. Despite the critical role of budgeting in ensuring financial sustainability and long-term success, there remains a significant gap in understanding how start-ups in this region develop and implement their budgeting strategies. Given the rapidly evolving business landscape and economic uncertainties, it is essential to examine these budgeting practices to provide empirical evidence on their influence on financial performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship and influence of budgeting practices on the financial performance of start-up businesses. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of start-up businesses concerning the number of years of business operation, asset size, and number of employees?
2. What is the level of budgeting practices in terms of resource allocation, budget planning, financial forecasting, and budget control of start-up businesses?
3. What is the level of financial performance in terms of profitability, growth in sale and liquidity of start-up businesses?
4. Is there a significant relationship between budgeting practices and the financial performance of start-up businesses?

Literature Review

Budgeting Practices

Budgeting is a form of planning since it predicts future events and how activities should be managed (Njahi, 2017). SMEs often face unique budgeting challenges, including limited financial expertise and resources. Risteska et al. (2023) found that SMEs encounter difficulties in budget planning and decision-making. Insufficient budget control mechanisms can lead to overspending and mismanagement of resources. Hence, a study by Zhang (2019) highlighted that about 31% of companies experience practical problems due to inadequate budget control, emphasizing the need for robust monitoring systems.

One significant budgeting challenge faced by small business owners is the failure to account for irregular or unforeseen expenses (Grzesiak, 2023). A common budgeting shortfall is the absence of a dedicated rainy-day or contingency fund, leaving businesses financially vulnerable in unexpected situations (Dye et al., 2021). This budgeting gap has a substantial impact on financial performance, often leading to cash flow difficulties and operational inefficiencies (Otoo, 2024). Effective budgeting is crucial for business success, particularly in tracking and evaluating financial performance (Mutabari & Warui, 2023). In many cases, poor financial performance stems from the adoption of ineffective budgeting practices, underscoring the need for strategic and well-structured budgeting approaches (Ariza et al., 2023).

Resource Allocation. Resource allocation, also known as resource scheduling, involves determining and distributing financial and material resources across various business tasks within a specific timeframe (Gupta, 2023). Many organizations face challenges due to limited resources, making prioritization a complex process. Research indicates that budget constraints often lead to inefficiencies and an inequitable distribution of resources (Garcia & Weiss, 2017). Akeem (2017) highlighted the critical role of resource allocation in business operations, emphasizing that budgets should be strategically managed to prevent financial waste. Additionally, developing budgeting proficiency enables businesses to create effective financial plans, ensuring funds are available to support future growth and enhance overall performance (Chepnetich, 2016).

Budget Planning. Lasak (2022) pointed out that efficient budget planning is crucial for the financial management of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Management is often concerned that involving staff members could result in lengthy discussions, hinder the budgeting process, and make decision-making more difficult due to opposing opinions (Van der Stede & Chenhall, 2015). For this reason, management opts to exclude workers from the budgeting process to minimize the risks associated with it, like the problem of mistrust that exists between management and the employees. Thus, Kamau et al. (2017) concluded that the adoption of a more organized budgeting strategy can result in heightened sales revenues for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

Financial Forecasting. Enterprises often faced challenges in forecasting their financial outlook resulting in flawed predictions, subsequently causing less-than-ideal budgeting choices (Henschel & Durst, 2016). SMEs typically lack the expertise needed to conduct robust financial forecasting. Many small businesses lack dedicated financial analysts, and the responsibility often falls on managers without formal training in finance (Kader, 2019). Due to the smaller scale of operations, many SMEs lack the budget for advanced forecasting tools or software, which are commonly used in larger organizations. As a result, SMEs often rely on simple techniques, such as trend analysis, which may not be sufficient for accurate financial projections (Cohen & Tyszka, 2018). Moreover, external factors, such as changes in government policy, inflation, or economic downturns, pose significant challenges for SMEs in their forecasting efforts. The unpredictable nature of these externalities complicates the task of forecasting, as these factors are difficult to quantify and often lead to large forecasting errors (Hughes et al., 2021).

Budget Control. A major issue in SME budget control is the use of inadequate or overly simplistic budgeting techniques. Many SMEs rely on basic approaches such as incremental budgeting, which does not adequately account for changes in the business environment or strategic goals (Dimitriou et al., 2021). In addition, they often lack financial experts or dedicated budget managers, which leads to a lack of professional oversight in budgeting processes. Many managers in SMEs do not have formal financial training, which can lead to miscalculations and errors in budget forecasting and control (Jones & Thomas, 2020). Thus, ongoing monitoring and adjustment of the budget are essential for effective budget control, but many SMEs lack the necessary processes or systems to track budget performance regularly. Managers may not review budgets frequently or may fail to adjust for unforeseen changes in the business environment (Horngren et al., 2017). Henceforth, the regular exercise of budget control enhances the preparation of sound decision-making and efficient communication between the top and subordinate managers (Matsoso et al., 2021).

Financial Performance

Wang et al. (2023) highlighted that financial performance is often influenced by external factors such as economic conditions,

regulatory changes, and market competition. One of the most significant challenges SMEs face in achieving strong financial performance is the difficulty in accessing external finance. Due to the perceived high risk associated with SMEs, financial institutions often hesitate to provide loans, forcing these businesses to rely on internal sources of funding or short-term credit (Beck et al., 2018). This limited access to finance constrains the growth potential of SMEs, preventing them from investing in innovation, expanding operations, or strengthening their market position (Ayyagari et al., 2020). Additionally, Ozturk and Aktas (2019) noted that firms exposed to economic downturns often experience drastic fluctuations in financial performance. These fluctuations, if not properly analyzed, may be misinterpreted as signs of operational inefficiency rather than the result of external economic pressures.

Moreover, SMEs often face challenges with delayed customer payments, which disrupt cash flow and hinder their ability to meet short-term financial obligations (Njoroge & Gathaiya, 2021). Additionally, limited economies of scale, inefficiencies in production processes, and rising input costs negatively impact profitability (Musabende & Opiyo, 2020). The lack of proper cost accounting systems and weak managerial control over expenditures further exacerbate these financial constraints (Haldma & Lääts, 2021). Another critical issue is the lack of financial literacy among SME owners and managers. Insufficient knowledge of financial management—such as budgeting, financial analysis, and forecasting—often leads to poor decision-making and suboptimal financial performance (Johnson & Scholes, 2019). Furthermore, SMEs are highly vulnerable to external economic factors, including inflation, currency fluctuations, and shifts in consumer demand (Fischer & Naughton, 2020). In competitive markets, SMEs also struggle to differentiate their products and services, making it even more challenging to sustain revenue growth (Rey, 2021).

Profitability. Profitability is a key measure of a firm's financial success, reflecting how much it earns relative to its size and overall performance (Horton, 2024). Many SMEs struggle with ineffective financial management practices, which directly impact their profitability. Weak cost accounting systems, improper budgeting, and inadequate cash flow management contribute to unnecessary expenditures and financial inefficiencies (Haldma & Lääts, 2021). Additionally, poor inventory management often leads to overstocking or stock shortages, increasing costs and limiting sales opportunities (Johnson & Scholes, 2019). The limited adoption of technology and innovation further hampers SME profitability, as many lack the resources and expertise to invest in modern solutions that enhance productivity and efficiency (Nguyen et al., 2021). Delgado and Torres (2019) emphasized that companies prioritizing return on investment (ROI) actively engage in continuous evaluation and optimization of their investment strategies, leading to improved financial outcomes. Similarly, Smith and Wesson (2020) concluded that optimizing operational efficiency is a crucial factor in enhancing ROI and overall profitability.

Growth in Sale. The growth in sale calculates how much money the business can make from sales over a given time frame (Kelwig, 2022). Moreover, the study of Tartaglione (2019) discussed that many businesses experience stagnation or decline in customer numbers due to insufficient brand loyalty and ineffective customer relationship strategies. Similarly, businesses may experience a plateau or decrease in customer growth if they fail to meet evolving customer expectations, especially in sectors heavily influenced by digital marketing and social media dynamics (Kumar & Pansari, 2016). High customer acquisition costs make it crucial for SMEs to retain existing clients, yet many fail to implement effective loyalty programs or after-sales services (Rey, 2021).

The study of Grönroos (2020) highlighted that businesses with strong customer relationship management systems tend to experience sustained growth in their sales performance. Furthermore, Armstrong and Kotler (2019) provided further evidence that one factor that contributes to sales growth is the implementation of effective marketing strategies. Businesses that focus on targeted marketing efforts, product diversification, and promotional activities tend to attract and retain customers more successfully, leading to increased sales over time.

Liquidity. Abdul (2018) defined liquidity as a business's ability to meet its current liabilities, which is closely linked to the composition and adequacy of its working capital. Atrill and McLaney (2019) highlighted that effective liquidity management is essential for maintaining financial stability, as poor monitoring of cash inflows and outflows can lead to cash shortages. Without proper oversight, businesses may struggle to meet payroll, supplier obligations, and other operational expenses (Johnson & Scholes, 2019). Additionally, over-reliance on seasonal revenues without adequate planning heightens liquidity risks (Musabende & Opiyo, 2020). Fixed expenses such as rent, wages, utilities, and loan repayments must be met regardless of revenue fluctuations, placing further financial strain on businesses (Porter, 2020). Rising costs of raw materials and supply chain inefficiencies exacerbate liquidity challenges, limiting a company's ability to maintain stable operations (Christopher, 2021). Insufficient liquidity reserves may force SMEs to cut costs by reducing employee wages, delaying supplier payments, or scaling back investments in growth initiatives (Rey, 2021). Thus, Bates et al. (2018) emphasized that firms with higher cash reserves are better equipped to navigate economic downturns and market fluctuations, as these reserves serve as a financial buffer against unexpected challenges.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the relationship between budgeting practices and the financial performance of start-up businesses. Strangor and Walinga (2019) conducted a study that explains how descriptive research design is utilized to provide a detailed representation of events, individuals, or circumstances, while correlational research identifies variable relationships and predicts outcomes based on existing data. Bloomfield and Fisher (2019) further emphasized that correlational

research employs quantitative techniques to quantify the strength and direction of relationships among variables. The study is descriptive as it evaluated the level of budgeting practices, in the aspects of resource allocation, budget planning, financial forecasting, and budget control, alongside the financial performance in terms of profitability, sales growth, and liquidity of start-up businesses. It is also correlational, as it aimed to determine the relationship between budgeting practices and financial performance.

Respondents

The study was carried out in the municipalities of Pigcawayan, Alamada, Libungan, Midsayap, and Aleosan (PALMA). The chosen geographical area contains newly established businesses. Moreover, the study gathered responses from 75 respondents, with 15 participants from each of the five municipalities to ensure fair representation and to determine the relationship between budgeting practices and financial performance of start-up businesses. The survey involved the owners and managers of various start-up businesses that were operating for five years and below from the municipalities mentioned above.

Instrument

The study employed a survey questionnaire adapted from Owino (2023) with minor modifications to align with the research objectives. The questionnaire consisted of three sections. The first section captured demographic data, including years of operation, asset size, and employee count within the start-up business sector. The second section assessed budgeting practices, focusing on resource allocation, budget planning, financial forecasting, and budget control. The third section evaluated financial performance indicators such as profitability, sales growth, and liquidity. A five-point Likert scale was used for the second and third sections, ranging from Strongly Agree (5) to Strongly Disagree (1), allowing respondents to indicate their level of agreement with the provided statements. Furthermore, the researchers established a face validity by seeking expert judgement from their teacher, adviser, and validators in modifying the research instrument. Furthermore, it was provided in the original instrument the reliability coefficient of the questionnaire. The overall Cronbach's alpha value for financial performance was "0.905" and for budgeting practices was "0.931" making the instrument deemed reliable.

Procedure

This study employed a structured survey questionnaire as the primary method for data collection. Before initiating the data collection process, formal approval was secured from the Dean of the College of Business and Accountancy. The researchers also obtained lists of start-up businesses from the Business Permit and Licensing Office (BPLO). Following the Dean's approval, the researchers issued a formal request for participation to the owners or managers of start-up businesses through an official letter, co-signed by the researchers and endorsed by their academic adviser. After the approval of the individuals' involved, the researchers distributed the questionnaires in the locality, and then retrieved all of the completed questionnaires. The data were meticulously compiled and subsequently submitted to a qualified statistician for analysis using appropriate statistical tools and methodologies to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the findings.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers utilized a modified edition of the questionnaire originally established by Owino (2023), for both the budgeting practices and financial performance making some relatively small modifications in order to reflect the context of the research. Throughout the entire procedure of modifications, the revised questionnaire was passed for validation. Furthermore, it was provided in the original instrument the reliability coefficient of the questionnaire. Moreover, the respondents had voluntarily participated in the conduct of the survey and the responses are kept with utmost confidentiality to evade privacy violations. Recognizing the potential constraints on the respondents' time due to their professional responsibilities, a sufficient timeframe was provided for the completion of the questionnaires.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the result and findings of the study. The results are presented in tabular forms.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of years of business operations, asset size, and number of employees.

Based on the data presented in Table 1, the highest frequency is found among start-up businesses operating for zero (0) to two (2) years, representing fifty-one (51) out of seventy-five (75) respondents, or sixty-eight percent (68%) of the total. Conversely, the lowest frequency is observed in the group of businesses that have been operational for three (3) to four (4) years, comprising only one (1) business, which accounts for one percent (1.33%) of the seventy-five respondents. Regarding estimated total asset size, most respondents are from start-up businesses with assets less than Php 3,000,000, totaling fifty-six (56) or seventy-four-point sixty-seven percent (74.67%) of the total. In contrast, the smallest group consists of start-up businesses with assets ranging from Php15,000,000 to Php 100,000,000, which includes five (5) respondents or six-point sixty-seven percent (6.67%) of the total. Finally, concerning the estimated number of employees, the highest frequency is found among start-up businesses with one (1) to nine (9) employees,

accounting for seventy-four (74) respondents or ninety-eight-point sixty-seven percent (98.67%) of the total. Conversely, the remaining respondents represent start-up businesses with ten (10) to ninety-nine (99) employees, constituting one point thirty-three percent (1%) of the seventy-five respondents.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Profile of the Respondents</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Years of Business Operation		
0 - 2 years	51	68.00
2 - 3 years	16	21.33
3 - 4 years	1	1.33
4 - 5 years	7	9.33
Total	75	100.00
Asset Size		
Less than Php 3,000,000	56	74.67
More than Php3,000,000 – Php15,000,000	14	18.67
More than Php 15,000,000 – Php 100,000,000	5	6.67
Total	75	100.00
Number of Employees		
1 – 9 employees	74	98.67
10 – 99 employees	1	1.33
Total	75	100.00

Level of Budgeting Practices

Table 2. *Level of Budgeting Practices*

<i>Summary</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Resource Allocation	4.20	0.85	Strongly Agree	Very High
Budget Planning	4.12	0.85	Agree	High
Financial Forecasting	4.04	0.86	Agree	High
Budget Control	4.10	0.86	Agree	High
Grand Mean	4.12		Agree	High
Average Standard Deviation		0.86		

Table 2 presents the data on the level of budgeting practices in terms of resource allocation, budget planning, financial forecasting, and budget control of start-up businesses. The results revealed resource allocation as the highest indicator rated as Strongly Agree with an overall mean of 4.20 and a standard deviation of 0.85. Conversely, the lowest indicator is financial forecasting rated as Agree with an overall mean of 4.04 and a standard deviation of 0.86. With these figures, the level of budgeting practices in start-up businesses is rated as Agree with a grand mean of 4.12 and an average standard deviation of 0.86.

Level of Financial Performance

Table 3. *Level of Financial Performance*

<i>Summary</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Profitability	4.12	0.73	Agree	High
Growth in Sale	3.93	0.76	Agree	High
Liquidity	3.96	0.85	Agree	High
Grand Mean	4.02		Agree	High
Average Standard Deviation		0.78	Agree	High

Table 3 shows the data on the level of financial performance in terms of profitability, growth in sale, and liquidity. The results reveal that the profitability indicator obtained the highest overall mean of 4.12 with a standard deviation of 0.73 and rated as Agree. Contrastingly, the indicator growth in sale garnered the lowest overall mean of 3.93 with a standard deviation of 0.76 and a description of Agree. With these figures, the level of financial performance in start-up business is rated as Agree with a grand mean of 4.02 and an average standard deviation of 0.78.

Relationship Between Budgeting Practices and Financial Performance

Table 4 presents the data on the relationship between budgeting practices and the financial performance of start-up businesses using Pearson correlation. It displays data indicating the occurrence of a moderate positive and statistically significant correlation ($r = 0.499$) between the variables of budgeting practices and financial performance at a significance level of 0.05 (two-tailed).

This is derived from an analysis of sample size conducted to seventy-five (75) data points, which indicates that there is a moderately positive correlation between budgeting practices and financial performance.

Table 4. *Relationship between Budgeting Practices and Financial Performance*

Variables	R – value	Interpretation	P – value	Indication	Decision
Budgeting Practices	0.499*	Moderate Positive Correlation	0.000	Significant	Reject Null Hypothesis (Ho1)

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

According to the frequency and percentage distributions, the majority of the start-up business have been operating for zero (0) to two (2) years with an asset size of less than Php 3,000,000 and composed of one (1) to nine (9) employees.

In general, the level of budgeting practices in start-up business is high. In terms of resource allocation, the results revealed a very high level of resource allocation as the business prepares budgets to help monitor its performance. When it comes to the budget planning, the results showed a high level as the business follows weekly/monthly/quarterly plans for expenses. Moreover, start-up business exhibits a high level of financial forecasting as the business always purchases what is budgeted for. Lastly, in the budget control element of budgeting practices results showed a high level as the budgeting helps to control inventory.

Furthermore, the level of financial performance of start-up business is high in general. In the aspect of profitability, start-up business exhibits a high-level degree of profitability as the business focuses on increasing return on investment. When it comes to the growth in sale aspect, results showed a high degree of growth in sale as the business' sales level of start-up business has been growing over time. Lastly, in terms of liquidity, the results revealed a high level of liquidity as the business has a favorable liquidity position.

Following the careful interpretation of the results, it is found that there exists a statistically significant and strong positive relationship between budgeting practices and financial performance. Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between budgeting practices and financial performance is therefore rejected.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, several key conclusions can be drawn. First, a significant proportion of the surveyed start-up businesses have been operating for zero (0) to two (2) years, with the majority having one (1) to nine (9) employees and an asset size of less than Php 3,000,000 being categorized as micro-enterprises. Second, the level of budgeting practices within the start-up business sector is very high, particularly in terms of resource allocation, budget planning, forecasting, and budget control. Third, the level of business performance is generally high, within the context of profitability, growth in sales and liquidity. Furthermore, the study's results confirm a significant and positive relationship between budgeting practices and the financial performance of start-up businesses. This suggest that adopting structured budgeting practices enhances the financial stability and growth of start-up businesses by improving resource allocation, decision-making, and risk management. This highlights the need for start-ups to prioritize budgeting as a strategic tool for long-term financial success.

To enhance financial performance, businesses should establish a clear petty cash policy, including withdrawal limits, monitoring methods, and regular reconciliations to prevent misuse. Engaging key employees in the budgeting process through structured methods such as planning meetings or surveys can improve financial decision-making. Additionally, start-ups should enhance forecasting by utilizing available data, considering various scenarios, and formulating strategic plans to ensure accurate budgeting despite limited historical data. Lastly, setting SMART financial goals and conducting regular budget reviews, such as quarterly assessments, allows businesses to adapt to market changes and improve overall financial performance.

References

- Abdul, E. O. (2018, March 19). Entrepreneurial skills and growth of Small and Medium Enterprise (SMEs): A comparative analysis of Nigerian entrepreneurs and Minority entrepreneurs in the UK. Retrieved from University of Wales Trinity Saint David: https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/86751/1/MPRA_paper_86751.pdf
- Afunadula, B. (2018), "Current mortality rate of SMEs Will Kill private sector – economist warns", PML Daily, available at: www.pmeldaily.com/business/2018/05/current-mortality-rate-of-smeswillkill-private-sector-economist-warns.html (accessed 20 August 2018).
- Agbana, J., Ibrahim, U. A., & Maitala, F. (2023) An Exploration of the Impact of Financial Risk on the Financial Performance of Quoted Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.
- Akeem, L. B. (2017). Effect of cost control and cost reduction techniques in organizational performance. *International business and management*, 14(3), 19-26.
- Anoos, Jose Marie & Anoos, M & Ferrater-Gimena, Judy & Ferrater-Gimena, O & Etcuban, Jonathan & Dinauanao, Aahron & Philip, Joel & Macugay, Iana & Velita, Lolita. (2020). *Financial Management Of Micro, Small, And Medium Enterprises In Cebu, Philippines*. 9. 53-76.
- Ariza, K. G. N. A., Reyes, A. P., Rocha, A. H. M., Perez, R. C., & Santana, C. I. B. (2023). The Relationship between Budgeting Practices and Financial Performance of Housing Construction Firms in Nairobi City County, Kenya. *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research*, 11(7), 7–16. <https://doi.org/10.20431/2349-0349.1107002>

- Armstrong, G., & Kotler, P. (2019). *Marketing: An Introduction* (14th ed.). Pearson.
- Atrill, P., & McLaney, E. (2019). *Financial Management for Decision Makers*. Pearson.
- Ayyagari, M., Beck, T., & Demirgüç-Kunt, A. (2020). Small and medium enterprises across the globe: A new database. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No. 3841. <https://doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-3841>
- Bates, T. W., Kahle, K. M., & Stulz, R. M. (2018). Why do US firms hold so much more cash than they used to? *Journal of Finance*, 64(5), 1985-2021.
- Beck, T., Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Maksimovic, V. (2018). Financing patterns around the world: Are small firms different? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 89(3), 467-487. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2008.03.002>
- Bloomfield, J., & Fisher, M. J. (2019). Quantitative research design. *Journal of the Australasian Rehabilitation Nurses Association*, 22(2), 27-30.
- Chepngetich, P. (2016). Effect of financial literacy and performance SMEs. Evidence from Kenya. Evidence from Kenya.
- Cohen, M., & Tyszka, J. (2018). Financial forecasting practices of small businesses. *Small Business Economics*, 51(2), 443-459. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-017-9942-x>
- Dela Cruz, R. M., & Gonzales, A. B. (2021). Financial constraints: Its impact on access to financing of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Calapan City. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 10(3), 245-255.
- Delgado, M., & Torres, L. (2019). Continuous optimization of ROI-focused business strategies. *Business Optimization Journal*, 12(3), 115-127.
- Dimitriou, A., Papadopoulos, T., & Kyriakou, C. (2021). Budgeting practices and challenges in small businesses: A review. *Small Business Economics*, 56(1), 123-137. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-019-00292-1>
- Dolorso, K. G. B. (2023). FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES OF MICROENTERPRISES IN QUEZON CITY. Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8030998> experimental research designs to understand behaviour. Introduction to Psychology.
- Edem, D. B. (2017). Liquidity management and performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria (1986-2011): An investigation. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 5(3), 146-161.
- Fischer, T., & Naughton, R. (2020). The impact of external economic shocks on small business performance. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 58(4), 763-785. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsbm.12372>
- Garcia, E., & Weiss, E. (2017). Resource allocation and student achievement: An analysis of school funding equity. *Educational Policy*, 31(2), 180-204.
- Grönroos, C. (2020). *Service Management and Marketing: Managing the Service Profit Logic* (4th ed.). Wiley
- Grzesiak, G. (2023, September 21). 12 common mistakes to avoid when budgeting for small businesses - Grit Daily News. Grit Daily News. <https://gritdaily.com/mistakes-when-budgeting-for-small-businesses/>
- Gupta, O. (2023, March 18). What is Resource Allocation, and Why is it Important? Resources Library.
- Haldma, T., & Lääts, K. (2021). Cost management practices and SME profitability: A comparative analysis. *Management Accounting Research*, 38, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mar.2021.100690>
- Haldma, T., & Lääts, K. (2021). Cost control practices and profitability among SMEs in Estonia. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 22(1), 17-35. <https://doi.org/10.3846/jbem.2021.13849>
- Henschel, T., & Durst, S. (2016, August 2). Risk management in Scottish, Chinese and German small and medium-sized enterprises: a country comparison. Retrieved from InsiderScience Online: <https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/abs/10.1504/IJESB.2016.078048>
- Horngren, C. T., Sundem, G. L., & Stratton, W. O. (2017). *Introduction to management accounting* (16th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Horton, M. (2024, August 7). The difference between profitability and profit. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/ask/answers/012715/what-difference-between-profitability-and-profit.asp>
- Hughes, L., Clarke, G., & McKeown, R. (2021). Navigating external uncertainty in SME financial forecasting. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 16(3), 55-72. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v16n3p55>
- Jones, C., & Thomas, R. (2020). Challenges in financial planning and budget control in SMEs. *Journal of Business and Financial Management*, 12(2), 98-111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21597404.2020.1733208>

- Johnson, G., & Scholes, K. (2019). *Exploring corporate strategy* (10th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Kader, M. (2019). The role of managerial expertise in financial forecasting: Evidence from SMEs. *Journal of Financial Research*, 43(2), 221-239. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfir.12152>
- Kamau, J. K., Rotich, G., & Anyango, W. (2017). Effect of budgeting process on budget performance of state corporations in Kenya: A case of Kenyatta National Hospital.
- Kelwig, D. (2022, March 13). Sales growth rate: Calculation + growth strategies. *Zendesk Blog*. <https://www.zendesk.com/blog/sales-growth/>
- Kumar, V., & Shah, D. (2019). Revisiting the relationship between marketing and sales performance. **Journal of Marketing Research**, 56(2), 321-334.
- Lasak, P. (2022). The role of financial technology and entrepreneurial finance practices in funding small and medium-sized enterprises.
- Matsoso, M. L., Nyathi, M., & Nakpodia, F. A. (2021). An assessment of budgeting and budgetary controls among small and medium-sized enterprises: evidence from a developing economy. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 11(4), 552-577. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jaee-04-2020-0082>
- Musabende, N., & Opiyo, R. (2020). Cost control measures in small enterprises: A case study of Nairobi SMEs. *International Journal of Economics and Business Research*, 19(2), 88-103. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEER.2020.107620>
- Mutabari, K. F., & Warui, F. (2023). The Relationship between Budgeting Practices and Financial Performance of Housing Construction Firms in Nairobi City County, Kenya. *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR)*, 11(7).
- Nguyen, T. H., Pham, D. N., & Tran, P. T. (2021). Digitalization and SME profitability: The case of Southeast Asia. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 57(3), 812-834. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1540496X.2021.1881043>
- Njahi, J. T. (2017). Effect of Financial Management Practices On Financial Performance of County
- Njoroge, L., & Gathaiya, C. (2021). Cash flow management practices in SMEs and their effect on financial performance: A case study of small businesses in Kenya. *Journal of Financial Studies*, 43(2), 112-126. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11569-021-00373-1>
- Otoo, F. N. K. (2024). Assessing the influence of financial management practices on organizational performance of small- and medium-scale enterprises. *Vilakshan – XIMB Journal of Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/xjm-09-2023-0192>
- Ozturk, A. B., & Aktas, R. (2019). The effects of economic uncertainty on corporate performance: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 20(3), 745-763.
- Porter, M. (2020). *The impact of fixed expenses on business sustainability*. Harvard Business Press.
- Rey, M. (2021). The competitive dynamics of SMEs in emerging markets: Financial performance and strategic management. *Small Business Economics*, 56(2), 341-359. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-019-00292-1>
- Risteska, A., Risteska, F., & Tanusevski, I. (2023). Budgeting practices and their impact on SMEs' financial performance. *Timisoara Journal of Economics and Business*, 16(1), 89-105. <https://doi.org/10.2478/tjeb-2023-0006>
- Smith, J., & Wesson, R. (2020). Lean Management and ROI: Optimizing Operational Efficiency. *Journal of Business Strategies*, 45(2), 123-134.
- Stangor, C., & Walinga, J. (2019). 3.5 psychologists use descriptive, correlational, and
- Tartaglione, A. M., Cavacece, Y., Russo, G., & Granata, G. (2019). A Systematic Mapping Study on Customer Loyalty and Brand Management. *Administrative Sciences*, 9(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.3390>
- Van der Stede, W. A., & Chenhall, R. H. (2015). Top-down budgeting and the trade-off between control and employee input. *Management Accounting Research*, 27, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mar.2015.01.003>
- Wang, H., Mao, K., Wu, W., & Luo, H. (2023). Fintech inputs, non-performing loans risk reduction and bank performance improvement. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 90, 102849.
- Zhang, Y. (2019). Budget control issues and their impact on financial performance. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 10(6), 55-61. <https://ijbmi.org/papers/Vol%2810%296/Ser-1/I1006015561.pdf>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Sarah Jane B. Orillosa, DBM

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Charlene Mae P. Acut

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Hannah Shayne U. Cabante

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines

Janna O. Trinidad

Notre Dame of Midsayap College – Philippines